

Collective Interactions of Excitons in Halide Perovskite Nanocrystal Superlattices

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ABSTRACT: Collective optical properties can emerge from an ordered ensemble of emitters, due to interactions between the individual units. Superlattices of halide perovskite nanocrystals exhibit collective light emission, influenced by dipole-dipole interactions between simultaneously excited nanocrystals. This coupling changes both the emission energy and rate compared with emission of uncoupled nanocrystals. We demonstrate how quantum confinement governs the nature of coupling between the nanocrystals in the ensemble. The extent of confinement is modified by controlling the nanocrystal size, or by compositional control over the Bohr radius. In superlattices made of weakly confined nanocrystals, the collective emission is red-shifted with a faster emission rate, showing key characteristics of superfluorescence. In contrast, the collective emission of stronger quantum-confined nanocrystals is blue-shifted, with a slower emission rate. Both types of collective emission exhibit correlative multiphoton emission bursts, showing distinct photon bunching emission statistics. The quantum confinement changes the preferred alignment of transition dipoles within the nanocrystal, switches the relative dipole orientation between neighbors, resulting in opposite collective optical behaviors. Our results extend these collective effects to relative high temperatures, and provide new understanding of exciton interactions and collective emission phenomena at the solid state.

The characteristics of a typical emitter are dictated by Fermi's golden rule, with the transition rate proportional to the oscillator strength. However, in the case of multiple interacting emitters, this premise is modified in a non-trivial manner according to the nature of the collective interaction. In the case of several identical emitters located within a small volume, coherent collective coupling through common vacuum modes of the electromagnetic field may result in a faster emission rate by a process called superradiance, first described by Dicke in the 1950s¹. In this process, an ensemble of emitters behaves as one large transition dipole with an oscillator strength proportional to the number of coupled emitters $N^{2,3}$. Dicke superradiance is commonly observed in dense atomic gases⁴, and recently reported in solid

state semiconductor systems⁵⁻⁷. However, many semiconductor systems deviate from the ideal superradiance model framework due to dipole-dipole interactions between the emitters. Herein we report the effects of quantum confinement on dipole-dipole influenced collective emission of perovskite nanocrystal (NC) ensembles. We control the type of dipole-dipole coupling by either changing the nanocrystal size or halide composition, resulting in vastly different modes of correlative collective light emissions both spectrally and temporally.

Insight into the collective emission resulting from dipole-dipole interactions between emitters is found in the exciton interaction theory, developed by Kasha in the 1960s^{8,9}. When several emitters in proximity are simultaneously excited, Coulomb interactions between the transition dipoles of neighboring emitters are possible. As a result of these dipole-dipole interactions, the system experiences an energy splitting by the value of the dipole-dipole interaction energy J_C . In one of the coupled states, the transition dipoles are aligned in the same direction (triplet for a dimer), while the other state has the transition dipoles in opposite directions (singlet for a dimer). The state with aligned transition dipoles has an oscillator strength proportional to the number of interacting emitters, therefore showing similar characteristics to superradiance. For the case of a dimer, the dipole-dipole interaction energy is given by⁹:

$$J_C = \frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_1 \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_2 - 3(\boldsymbol{\mu}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{R}})(\boldsymbol{\mu}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{R}})}{4\pi\epsilon|\mathbf{R}|^3} [1]$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ is the transition dipole, $\hat{\mathbf{R}}$ is the vector connecting the two transition dipoles, and ϵ is the dielectric coefficient of the surrounding medium. In cases with negative interaction ($J_C < 0$, “head-to-tail” interaction), the triplet state has lower energy than the excited state of an individual emitter. Ground-triplet exciton transitions are optically allowed while ground-singlet are parity forbidden^{9,10}. Due to these symmetry considerations, negative interaction between emitters, commonly termed as J-aggregate, leads to a red-shifted coupled emission (Fig. 1a)¹⁰. Conversely, if the interaction is positive ($J_C > 0$, “head-to-head” interaction), the triplet excitonic state has a higher energy than the excited state of an individual emitter. Therefore, positive interaction between emitters, known as H-aggregate, results in a spectral blue-shift (Fig. 1b)¹⁰.

Figure 1. Underlying mechanism of dipole-dipole coupling influenced collective emission behavior. (a-b) Energy level diagrams for Coulomb dipole-dipole interaction between transition dipoles for a dimer of (a) “head-to-tail” interaction J-aggregate, and (b) “head-to-head” interaction H-aggregate. The transition between the ground and excited coupled states is only allowed to the state with aligned transition dipole moments. This bright state is the lower/upper coupled state for J/H aggregates respectively, leading to either spectral red-shift or blue-shift in the coupled emission.

H/J aggregate behavior is commonly found in aggregates of organic dye molecules¹⁰⁻¹², and clusters of organic semiconductors^{13,14}. In these organic systems, the excitons are highly localized Frenkel excitons, positioned mainly between the electron donating and electron withdrawing groups^{10,15}. As a result, the type of interaction is mainly dictated by the relative orientation between chromophores in the

cluster. However, in many solid-state semiconductors the excitons are delocalized Wannier-Mott excitons, which are free to move within the volume of the crystal¹⁶⁻¹⁸. This theoretically opens the possibility of changing the collective interaction and emission characteristics without influencing the geometry of the cluster.

Ordered superlattice (SL) assemblies of nanocrystal quantum dots are promising platforms for such manipulation of the collective optical properties. The first observation of collective superfluorescent emission from CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal superlattices was reported by Raino et.al.⁵. This collective emission was apparent only in ordered superlattices and measured at a cryogenic temperature of 5K. This collective emission showed a distinct red-shift with an accelerated emission rate relative to the emission of uncoupled nanocrystals. Several theoretical explanations for this collective accelerated emission were suggested, including Dicke superradiance and exciton delocalization^{5,19-21}. Following works showed collective emission from binary/ternary superlattices made from mixtures of CsPbBr₃ and Fe₃O₄ or LaF₃ nanocrystals, which arranged in many different structures²²⁻²⁵. In these cases, the collective emission still originated from the coupling between CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. Utilizing these collective optical properties, especially from superlattices of cesium lead halide perovskite nanocrystals, is promising for implementation in various applications ranging from bright and efficient emitters to high-energy ultrafast detectors²⁶⁻²⁸. Therefore, the ability to control the type of coupling between nanocrystals and the resulting collective emission shown here is significant for these applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Formation of nanocrystal superlattices requires highly monodispersed and uniform nanocrystals²⁹. We synthesized monodispersed colloidal CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals using the procedure reported by Dong et.al.³⁰. Modifying the reaction temperature and Pb to halide precursor ratio allows size tunability of the nanocrystals (Fig. 2a-c). Monodispersed CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals with average edge sizes of $\langle L \rangle = 9.3 \pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$, $\langle L \rangle = 7.8 \pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$, and $\langle L \rangle = 6.3 \pm 0.4 \text{ nm}$ were obtained. Deposited nanocrystals self-assembled on the substrate creating three-dimensional cubic-packed rectangular superlattices, along with non-assembled areas between the superlattices acting as colloidal glassy films (Fig. S1). To probe the collective light emission, micro photoluminescence (PL) measurements were conducted at cryogenic liquid nitrogen temperature ($T = 80 \text{ K}$). All the measured superlattices showed two distinct emission peaks at 80K (Fig. 2d-f). We identify one of these emission peaks as spontaneous emission of individual uncoupled nanocrystals, and the other as cooperative emission of coupled nanocrystal systems. This determination is based on the PL of unorganized areas, and on temperature-dependent measurements.

Unlike the two PL peaks in superlattices, spectra of unorganized glassy film areas at 80K had only one PL peak (black dashed lines) which coincided with one of the two PL peaks of the superlattices. Therefore, we assign this peak to spontaneous emission of uncoupled nanocrystals. The additional PL peak in superlattices is of coupled nanocrystal systems, which require the high structural order found in the superlattices. Different superlattices showed different ratios between the emission peaks, likely due to defects in the superlattices³¹ and reduced structural order required for the collective emission.

An additional method for identifying the coupled emission is by the temperature evolution of the PL spectra as shown in Fig. 2g-i. PL spectra of superlattices at a temperature range of $200 \text{ K} < T < 273 \text{ K}$ showed only a single peak, which red-shifts during cooling due to crystallographic changes in the perovskite structure³²⁻³⁴. Below a threshold temperature of $T < 180-200 \text{ K}$, a second emission peak formed. As coupling between excited nanocrystals requires interaction between transition dipoles, thermal fluctuations at higher temperatures hinder this process^{35,36}. The collective emission was reversible with the temperature changes, as heating above the threshold temperature made it disappear, and cooling it below the threshold temperature again made it reappear. This indicates that the additional peak is not the result of irreversible changes to the system. Moreover, the intensity of the collective

emission increases greatly, upon a decrease in temperature, more than the intensity increment of the uncoupled nanocrystals. This is likely because reducing the temperature increases the probability of coupling between nanocrystals and consequently enhances the collective emission. Therefore, the emission peak at higher temperatures is again attributed to uncoupled nanocrystals, whereas the additional peak forming at lower temperatures (only in superlattices) is attributed to coupled nanocrystals.

Figure 2. Quantum-confinement tunable collective emission of halide perovskite nanocrystals. (a-c) TEM micrographs and size distribution histograms of the nanocrystal building blocks for (a) 9.3nm, (b) 7.8nm, and (c) 6.3nm cuboid-shaped CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. (d-f) PL spectrum at T=80K of superlattices made from (d) 9.3nm, (e) 7.8nm, and (f) 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. The coupled emission is (d-e) red-shifted or (f) blue-shifted relative to the uncoupled emission present in PL from nanocrystal glassy films (black dashed lines). (g-i) PL spectra at different temperatures of superlattices made from (g) 9.3nm, (h) 7.8nm, and (i) 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. In the larger nanocrystals a red-shifted peak, and in smaller nanocrystals a blue-shifted peak appears below a temperature of 180-200K.

Red-shifted coupled emission at cryogenic temperatures was previously reported in CsPbBr₃ superlattice as superfluorescent emission⁵. In our measurements however, the collective emission showed different spectral characteristics depending on the nanocrystal building blocks. In the cases of 9.3nm and 7.8nm nanocrystals, the coupled emission is red-shifted relative to the uncoupled peak. In contrast, superlattices made of smaller 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals showed drastically different coupled PL at temperatures of T ≤ 180K. The coupled nanocrystal emission in this case was blue-shifted relative to the uncoupled emission. In addition to the red-shift, we also observe spectral narrowing as

shown in Fig. 2 d-e. This is a known property of superfluorescent J-aggregates where the coupled emission is narrower by a factor of \sqrt{N} due to exchange narrowing³⁷. In the novel case of the blue-shifted coupled PL we do not observe a spectral narrowing but comparable width or broadening as commonly shown in molecular H-aggregates¹⁰. In terms of the exciton interaction theory discussed previously, superlattices of small CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals behave similarly to H-aggregates, while superlattices of larger nanocrystals behave like J-aggregates.

Figure 3. Temporal and correlative characteristics of the different collective emissions. (a-b) Time-resolved PL at 80K of superlattices made from (a) 7.8nm, and (b) 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. Average emission rates show (a) accelerated red-shifted coupled emission, and (b) slower emission rate for the blue-shifted coupled emission. (c-f) Second-order correlation function measurements, obtained with a Hanbury–Brown and Twiss set-up using pulsed excitation with a 10 MHz repetition rate, for SLs made from (c,e) 7.8nm, and (d,f) 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. Both red-shifted (e) and blue-shifted (f) collective emission of coupled nanocrystals show photon bunching at a zero time delay, while emission of the uncoupled nanocrystals (c,d) shows Poissonian photon emission statistics.

In addition to the spectral changes, the emerging collective emissions showed different temporal and correlative behaviors compared to uncoupled nanocrystal emission, depending on the type of coupling. In the case of collective red-shifted emission, the coupled emission has an accelerated decay rate relative to uncoupled nanocrystals, as shown by time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) in Fig. 3a. As the collective transition dipole of a J-aggregate is the sum of the interacting transition dipoles, this emission is accelerated by a factor of the number of coupled emitters in the collective system N :

$$\tau_C = \frac{\tau_1}{N} [2]$$

where τ_C , and τ_1 are the radiative lifetimes for the coupled system of emitters, and individual uncoupled emitters respectively. For this reason, J-aggregates are often characterized as having superfluorescent emission^{2,10,37}. In our case, the collective emission of superlattices made from 7.8nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals, showed 2-3 times higher emission rate than that of uncoupled nanocrystals. According to Eq.2, this indicates that the effective number of coupled emitters is 2-3 nanocrystals. This increase in emission rate is consistent with previously reported measurements of 2.7 times faster superfluorescent collective emission rate in CsPbBr₃ superlattices⁵. On the other hand, collective blue-shifted emission showed a slower emission rate than the uncoupled nanocrystals, as shown in Fig. 3b. This is a known

property of H-aggregates, as this type of coupling introduces a competing non-radiative decay process towards the dark state with opposite transition dipoles^{10,38}. Despite the longer lifetime in the collective blue-shifted emission, we do not attribute it to subradiant behavior in which the emission rate is slower with the increase of the number of coupled emitters in the system.

We additionally measured the emission statistics of coupled and uncoupled nanocrystals using Hanbury–Brown and Twiss set-up with pulsed excitation, to study the correlative properties of both types of coupling. Fig. 3c-f shows the second-order correlation function ($g^2(\Delta t)$) of the emitted light. Uncoupled emission from both samples showed a Poissonian distribution of photon arrival times, with $g^2(0) = 1$ (Fig. 3c-d). On the other hand, collective emission from both types of coupling showed pronounced photon bunching $g^2(0) > 1$, indicating a process of multi-photon emission bursts originating from the couplings (Fig. 3e-f)⁵. Second-order correlation function values from longer time ranges, accounting for the integral intensity of more excitation pulses, are shown in Fig. S4. The 7.8nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals showed $g^2(0) = 1.21 \pm 0.02$, and the 6.3nm sample, despite its slower collective emission rate, showed $g^2(0) = 1.24 \pm 0.01$. These bunching results are 9 and 16 times the standard deviation above average respectively. This indicates that despite the differences in spectral and temporal characteristics, both types of coupling resulted in correlative multi-photon emission.

Figure 4. Composition control over quantum confinement and the resulting collective emission. (a-b) PL spectrum at T=80K of superlattices made of anion exchanged (a) 7.8nm CsPb(Br_{0.5}I_{0.5})₃, and (b) 6.3nm CsPb(Br_{0.4}Cl_{0.6})₃ nanocrystals. The compositional changes modify the extent of quantum confinement and switch the collective spectral behaviors shown previously. (c-d) PL spectra at different temperatures of superlattices made of (c) 7.8nm CsPb(Br_{0.5}I_{0.5})₃, and (d) 6.3nm CsPb(Br_{0.4}Cl_{0.6})₃ nanocrystals. In chloride-exchanged nanocrystals a red-shifted peak, and in iodide-exchanged nanocrystals a blue-shifted peak appears at cryogenic temperatures. (e) Time-resolved PL at 80K of superlattice made of (right) 7.8nm CsPb(Br_{0.5}I_{0.5})₃, and (left) 6.3nm CsPb(Br_{0.4}Cl_{0.6})₃. (f) Measured coupled PL energy difference vs the extent of quantum confinement of the nanocrystal building blocks.

We wish to emphasize that despite the shared similarities between nanocrystal superlattices and molecular H/J aggregates, shown by the collective energy shifts and the time-resolved behaviors, there are also striking differences. For example, some systems of interacting emitters, including molecular aggregates, were measured as having anti-bunching emission statistics³⁹. However, these results are different from our observations as an emission from these entangled superradiant states is in the single-photon superradiance regime, meaning that even when a single photon is emitted the radiative rate is

enhanced due to the relaxation being from a symmetric delocalized state with an enhanced oscillator strength^{21,40}. Our observed photon bunching from perovskite nanocrystal superlattices, along with previous reports⁵, suggest interactions in the multi-excitation regime, resulting in multi-photon correlative emission.

In explaining the difference in collective emission between superlattices of large and small nanocrystals, we considered two options. One option is that a change in nanocrystal size leads to a difference in nanocrystal packing, thereby changing the conformation between neighboring transition dipoles. Recent works indeed showed that CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal superlattices packing is affected by changes in the nanocrystal size and colloidal softness^{41,42}. The second option is that coupling differences arise from the effect of quantum confinement. To determine which mechanism is more likely, we changed the extent of quantum confinement without significantly changing the nanocrystal size, and hence the related nanocrystal packing. This was achieved via a room temperature anion exchange method, which in halide perovskite nanocrystals is facile, topotactic, and greatly affecting the Bohr diameter of excitons in the nanocrystals^{43,44}. The anion exchange process was conducted on the 6.3 and 7.8nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals reported previously, to obtain mixed-halide nanocrystals with different amounts of iodide or chloride. This effectively changes the composition of the nanocrystal and the extent of quantum confinement without significant changes to the physical size or colloidal softness of the nanocrystals⁴³. The extent of quantum confinement x may be defined as:

$$x = \frac{d_B}{L} \quad [3]$$

where d_B is the Bohr diameter of excitons in the nanocrystal, and L is the nanocrystal size. The Bohr diameters of CsPbCl₃/CsPbBr₃/CsPbI₃ are 4nm/7nm/12nm, respectively reflecting the difference in the dielectric function of the perovskite matrix, and the effective mass of charge carriers⁴⁵. In the mixed halide nanocrystals, the Bohr diameter was determined by a weighted mean of the pure compositions. Anion exchange of Br⁻ to I⁻ increases the Bohr diameter and the extent of quantum confinement. Alternatively, Br⁻ to Cl⁻ exchange reduces the Bohr diameter, and therefore effectively decreases the extent of quantum confinement.

Composition control over quantum confinement did change the collective spectral and temporal behaviors. Superlattices made of iodide-exchanged 7.8nm CsPb(Br_{0.5}I_{0.5})₃ nanocrystals, with an effective Bohr diameter of 9.5nm, changed their previous red-shifted J-aggregate like collective emission behavior, and showed a coupled blue-shifted H-aggregate like behavior as a result of the quantum confinement (Fig. 4a,c). The same spectral behavior was observed in other confined iodide-exchanged 7.8nm CsPb(Br_{0.7}I_{0.3})₃, and CsPb(Br_{0.3}I_{0.7})₃ nanocrystals with effective Bohr diameters of 8.6nm, and 10.5nm respectively (Fig. S8). In addition, superlattices made of chloride-exchanged 6.3nm CsPb(Br_{0.4}Cl_{0.6})₃ nanocrystals, with an effective Bohr diameter of 5.8nm, changed their previous collective emission from blue-shifted H-aggregate like to a red-shifted J-aggregate like behavior as a result of the weaker quantum confinement (Fig. 4b,d).

In addition to the spectral changes in collective emission, the emission rates were modified by the anion exchange as well, shown by TRPL in Fig. 4e. Coupled PL of the iodide-exchanged nanocrystals showed a slower emission rate, while chloride-exchanged nanocrystals showed an accelerated emission by a factor of 2 relative to the uncoupled emission. Fig. 4f presents the energy difference between coupled and uncoupled emissions vs the extent of quantum confinement from 13 samples with nanocrystals of various compositions and sizes. In all nanocrystals with $x > 1$ the collective emission behavior was blue-shifted and behave similarly to H-aggregate, while all nanocrystals with $x < 1$ showed red-shifted J-aggregate like collective emission.

To better understand why quantum confinement changes the coupling behavior, we set out to measure the alignment of transition dipoles of the nanocrystals. In excitonic luminescent materials, light

emission has a cosine angular distribution with a peak oriented perpendicular to the transition dipole moment⁴⁶. Due to this angular distribution, it is possible to understand the orientation of transition dipoles in materials from angular-dependent emission patterns. This method was previously used to determine transition dipole orientation in molecules⁴⁷, layered nanomaterials⁴⁸, CdSe nanoplates⁴⁹, and CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals⁵⁰. We measured angular-dependent emission patterns locally from 2-3 columns of nanocrystals in the superlattice using cathodoluminescence (CL) scanning electron microscopy^{41,51}. The angular-resolved data was analyzed and plotted as polar maps shown in Fig. 5a-b, with each point corresponding to a different polar angle (θ) and azimuthal angle (φ)⁴⁷.

Emission from 7.8nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal superlattices was isotropic along φ , with most of the emission (80.3%) directed to low polar angles in the range of $\theta = 5 - 45^\circ$. The 6.3nm sample showed different angular-dependent emission patterns with preferred azimuthal angles. The preferred azimuthal angles were different for different superlattices in this sample as shown in Fig. S9. The 6.3nm nanocrystals showed polar angle directionality of $\theta = 5 - 45^\circ$ (57.9% of the emitted light) as well, but with an additional dominant emission (40.3%) at higher polar angles up to 68° . These differences in angular distribution are assigned to changes in preferred transition dipole orientation in the nanocrystals, which is affected by the size of the nanocrystals via quantum confinement. This is further supported by previous observations of transition dipole preferred alignment changes due to confinement in CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals^{50,52}.

Figure 5. Quantum confinement effects on transition dipole orientation and coupling type. (a-b) Angular resolved cathodoluminescence emission patterns measured from superlattices made of (a) 7.8nm, and (b) 6.3nm CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals. The upper panels show intensity vs polar angle θ along azimuthal axis of $\varphi=120^\circ/300^\circ$ marked in dashed lines on the 2D projections. (c) Schematic of coupled nanocrystal dimer with non-planar transition dipole conformation. (d) dipole-dipole coupling conformation factor calculation for non-planar transition dipoles as a function of inclination angle β , and angle between transition dipole planes α .

The introduced preferred transition dipole orientation in smaller nanocrystals leads to a different transition dipole conformation between neighboring nanocrystals, and therefore dictates the coupling type (Fig. 5c-d). If the transition dipole size ($|\mu|$) is the same for both coupled emitters in a dimer, the dipole-dipole coupling energy derived from Eq.1 is:

$$J_C = \frac{|\mu|^2 (\cos \alpha - 3 \cos^2 \beta)}{4\pi\epsilon R^3} [4]$$

where β is the angle between $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \vec{R} , and α is the angle between transition dipoles. In effect, the dipole-dipole interaction sign is governed by β and α angle dependent conformation factor (J_C^*). Below a critical inclination angle β_C (54.7° for $\alpha = 0^\circ$), $J_C < 0$ i.e. red-shift coupling. Meanwhile, for transition dipoles conformation with higher than critical inclination angle, $J_C > 0$ i.e. blue-shift coupling. From Eq.4 the critical inclination angle is given by:

$$\beta_C = \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\cos \alpha}{3}} \right) \quad [5]$$

Our measured transition dipole conformation agrees with the spectral behaviors we observed (Fig. 2e-f). In the 7.8nm nanocrystals, we expect $\alpha = 0^\circ$ due to the isotropic pattern in φ , from the emission directionality to small polar angles in θ we find that $\beta < 54.7^\circ$, and therefore the expected coupling behavior is indeed a red-shifted like J-aggregate as was observed. In the 6.3nm case, the measured high polar angle θ emission component indicates that $\beta > \beta_C(\alpha)$. Therefore, the extracted conformation of transition dipoles in this sample is expected to cause a blue-shift H-aggregate like coupling as was measured.

In conclusion, we report switching the collective optical behavior of perovskite nanocrystal superlattices between two distinct regimes. Merging Kasha exciton interaction theory with Dicke superradiance model provides a new understanding of exciton interactions and collective emission phenomena at the solid state. Using this understanding, we assign a key role for dipole-dipole interactions in the collective emission process, that is tuned through control over the quantum confinement. Weaker confined nanocrystals behave like J-aggregates with a coupled emission red-shift and an accelerated emission rate, while stronger confined nanocrystals behave like H-aggregates with a blue-shifted coupled emission and a reduced emission rate. Switching between these behaviors is possible by changing the nanocrystal size or halide composition. The demonstrated ability to tune collective light emission is especially important for future implementation of these nanomaterials in optoelectronic applications utilizing their emerging collective properties.

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Author Contributions

S.L. and Y.B. designed the experiments. S.L., O.B., S.S., and E.S. performed the measurements. R.S., K.C., R.L., and Y.O. aided with the experimental setup. S.L, A.G, and I.K implemented the theory.

S.L. analyzed the results, and wrote the manuscript with help from the rest of the co-authors.

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Experimental Methods:

Materials: Cesium Carbonate (99.9%, Aldrich), Hexane (A.R., Aldrich), Lead Bromide (99.998%, Aesar), Lead Chloride (99.999%, Aldrich), Lead Iodide (99 %, Aldrich), Octadecene (90%, Acros), Oleic acid (90%, Aldrich), Oleylamine (98%, Aldrich), Toluene (99.8%, Aldrich), Zinc Bromide (99.9%, Aesar).

All chemicals were used as purchased without further purification.

Synthesis of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals, anion exchange and superlattice preparation: First, Cs-oleate precursor was prepared in a 50 mL three-necked round-bottomed flask by dissolving Cs₂CO₃ (0.25 g) in a mixture of oleic acid (0.8 g) and octadecene (7 g) at 150 °C for 10 minutes under a N₂ atmosphere on a Schlenk line. The precursor solution of Pb and Br was prepared by dissolving PbBr₂ (75 mg) and a varying amount of ZnBr₂ in a mixture of octadecene (5 mL), oleic acid (2 mL), and oleylamine (2 mL) in a 25 mL three-necked round-bottomed flask under a N₂ atmosphere at 120 °C for 10 min. After the setting of the temperature of the precursor solution of Pb and Br, 0.4 mL of Cs precursor solution was injected to initiate the reaction. The reaction was quenched after few seconds in an ice water bath. The product was centrifuged twice at 9000 and 3500 rpm and dispersed in clean toluene to obtain the monodispersed nanocrystals. Anion exchange process was conducted in ambient conditions. halide stock solution was made by mixing 5ml of clean Toulene with 0.1ml of oleic acid, and 100mg of PbX₂ salt. 1ml of isolated nanocrystals in toluene was mixed with the desired amount of lead halide stock solution overnight to obtain mixed halide nanocrystals. The SLs were prepared by drop casting process of the nanocrystal solution in toluene on the desired substrate. Silicon wafer was used as substrate for SEM and PL characterization, and carbon film on 300 mesh copper grids for TEM characterization. 25μL volume was casted and dried under ambient conditions for several hours (usually 3-5h) followed by overnight vacuuming.

Liquid Nitrogen Micro Photoluminescence (PL), Time Resolved Photoluminescence (TRPL), and Photon Statistics Measurements: Spectroscopic characterizations were performed using an Edinburgh FLS1000 spectrometer coupled to Nikon Eclipse UPRIGHT microscope with a THMS350 V Linkam temperature-controlled vacuum cryogenic stage with LNP95. All the deposited nanocrystal samples were loaded into the cryostat and vacuumed to prevent ice formation, during temperature changes the system had 180s of stabilization time. The samples were excited either by Edinburgh Xe lamp, or Edinburgh 375nm or 405nm efficient pulse laser (EPL). TRPL measurements were performed in a multichannel scaling (MCS) mode with monochromator used for separating the coupled, and uncoupled emissions. Photon statistics and second-order correlation function measurements were conducted on the

same setup using 405nm EPL with an appropriate band pass filter and two avalanche photodiodes (Micro Photon Devices, 100 μm PDM SPAD), and 50:50 beamsplitter splitting the light between them.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Characterization: One drop of dilute nanocrystal solution in hexane (1:20 dilution) was cast onto a TEM grid (carbon film only on 300 mesh copper grid). The samples were observed in TEM mode with a Thermo Fisher/FEI Tecnai G² T20 S-Twin LaB₆ TEM operated at 200KeV, with a Gatan Rio9 CMOS camera.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):

High resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): One drop of dilute nanocrystal solution was casted on silicone substrate for SEM characterization using Zeiss Ultra-Plus FEG-SEM. Samples were placed at a working distance of 3 mm and measured using acceleration voltages between 1 and 5 KV.

Angular resolved Cathodoluminescence (CL) SEM: CL experiments were conducted on Thermo Fisher Apreo 2S scanning electron microscope with Delmic SPARC CL module equipped with a parabolic mirror. Beam energy of 10 keV was used with an electron probe current of 400 pA. the Electron beam spot size was estimated to be around 3 nm at 10 keV. The CL emission is analyzed with a high-speed CDD camera (Andor Newton 920). For angular resolved emission measurements, the system was equipped with band pass filter of 500/50nm, and the acquisition time was 5s.